

Product Quality Through Consumer Attitude Towards Purchase Decision Of Animal Feeds In Toba Samosir Regency

Author's Details:

Jarunjung Hutagaol¹, Nirwana Bangun², Sondang Ni Bulan Marbun³

¹University of Prima Indonesia, Faculty of Economics

^{2,3}University of Sisingamaraja XII, Faculty of Economics

Abstract: *The purpose of this study was to analyze factors that influenced product quality of animal feed through consumer attitude towards purchase decision of animal feed in Toba Samosir regency and to investigate the extent of product quality of animal feed through consumer outlook towards purchase decision of animal feed in Toba Samosir regency. This study used a descriptive method involving 100 respondents. The data were collected using questionnaires. The obtained data were further analyzed by using statistic formula, that was using multiple regression analysis.*

Keywords: *product quality, consumer outlook towards animal feed and purchase decision*

INTRODUCTION

Consumers' attitudes are the most important concepts in the study of consumer behavior. Every year, marketing managers spend a lot of funds to examine consumers' attitudes toward purchase decisions. Furthermore, they incur additional costs in influencing attitudes encountered through the activities of quality products of animal feed, sales promotion and other types of product quality of animal feed. By influencing consumer attitudes, marketers expect to influence consumers purchase behavior, since attitudes have become a key concept in psychology. Consumer attitudes are important psychological factors that marketers need to appreciate, as it is perceived to have a positive and strong correlation with behavior. In fact, attitude is considered as an influencing predictor to discover consumer behavior (Suryani, 2008). Furthermore, Suryani (2008: 159) argued that consumer attitudes are important psychological factors that marketers need to recognize, as it is considered to have a positive and strong correlation between information value and purchase decisions. This is because consumers who like or being positive towards a product derived from information value contained from the product, that they have strong purchase belief to decide and purchase the products they like. When reviewed in Toba Samosi Regency, based on Central Bureau of Statistics (BPS) in 2017, the number of livestock population consisted of 2,143 cows, which was 10,063 buffalos, 1,209 goats, and 37,964 pigs, and the commodities produce profits for production of animal feed. Therefore, in order to observe the extent to which consumer attitudes toward purchase decision of animal feed, it will be an assessment of consumer attitudes regarding purchase decision of animal feed in Toba Samosir".

LITERATURE REVIEW

Definition of Consumer Attitudes

Consumer attitudes are important psychological factors that marketers need to understand because as it is perceived to have a positive and strong correlation with behavior. In fact, attitude is considered as an influence predictor to discover consumer behavior (Suryani, 2008.). There is a close relation between attitudes and behaviors that they are considered important. The marketers attempt various efforts to develop a positive attitude, both towards the brand, the product or the company. Indicators of Consumer Attitudes by Schiffman and Kanuk (2004: 225) suggested that there were three components in attitude: a) Cognitive component (brand trust) b) Affective component (brand evaluation), c) Conative component (purchase intent)

Definition of Product Quality

According to *the American Society for Quality control*, Quality is "the totality of features and characteristic of a product or service that bears on its ability to satisfy given needs," which means the overall characteristics and features of a product or service that reflects its ability to satisfy the implied need. This definition is an understanding of consumer-centered quality, as it means that a salesperson has provided quality when his product or service meets or exceeds the consumer expectations, whether the customers have already been familiar with or unfamiliar with the brand. Indicators of Product Quality according to Mullins, Orville, Larreche, and Boyd are 1) Performance, 2) Durability (endurance), 3) Conformance to specifications, 4) Features, 5) Reliability, 6) Aesthetics, 7) Perceived quality.

Definition of Purchase Decision

According to Engel et. Al (2000: 31) purchase decision is the process of formulating various alternative measures in making a decision on one particular option in order to make a purchase. Consumers base their expectations on information they receive from sellers, friends and other sources. When sellers overestimate their product achievements, it will not meet consumer expectations and dissatisfaction. The greater is the gap between expectation and achievement, the greater is dissatisfaction of the consumer. It indicates that the consumers shall make an ingenuous statement concerning the product achievement to satisfy them. Hsu and Chang (2008) proposed indicators to measure purchase decisions as follows: 1. The inclination to use the product, 2. The inclination to purchase the product, 3. Prioritize the purchase of a product, 4. The willingness to sacrifice (time, cost, and energy) to obtain a product.

Hypothesis

H1 Consumer Attitudes have a positive and significant influence on purchase decision of animal feed in Toba Samosir regency
 H2 Product Quality positively and significantly influence towards purchase decision of animal feed in Toba Samosir Regency
 H3 Consumer Attitudes and Product Quality simultaneously have a positive and significant influence on purchase decision of animal feed in Toba Samosir regency.

RESEARCH METHODS

Research Setting and Timing

This research was conducted in the community of livestock owners of Toba Samosir Regency who use animal feed. While the time scheduled to accomplish the results of this study was estimated approximately three months from March to May of 2017.

Types and Data Sources

1. Quantitative Data.
2. Qualitative Data.

Population and Sample

As for population in this study were the livestock owners as an analysis unit in Toba Samosir regency in March 2017 in indefinite number. In this study, the population is unidentified, that determination of sample size of the population was using theory developed by Isac Michael (Siregar Syofian, 2011: 149). Based on the results of these calculations, the number of samples in this study amounted to 100 farmers. It used Accidental Sampling method.

Analysis Method

1. Classic Assumption Test Analysis
2. Multiple regression analysis using the formula:

$$Y = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e$$

Which :

Y = Purchase Decision

X1 = Consumer Attitude

X2 = Product Quality

B0, b1, b2, = regression coefficients

Any questionable indicator of the questionnaire used a Likert scale. This scale was used to measure attitudes, opinions, and perceptions of a person or group regarding social events or symptoms (Ridwan and Akdom, 2007). In the questionnaire used by the researcher, each question consisted of 5 (five) categories of answers, which were STS = 1, TS = 2, N = 3, S = 4, SS = 5.

3. Hypothesis Testing
 1. Validity Test
 2. Reliability Test
 3. Analysis of Determination Coefficient (R²)
 4. T-Test (Partial Test)
 5. F-Test (Simultaneous Test)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

DATA ANALYSIS

Descriptive statistics

Based on the results of the descriptive statistical analysis, it will represent the sample characteristics used in this study including the number of samples (N), mean of the sample (mean), maximum value, minimum value and standard deviation (σ) for each variable. The results of the descriptive analysis can be described in Table 4 below:

**Table 4
Descriptive Research Analysis**

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
PURCHASE DECISION	34,3800	4,53445	100
PRODUCT QUALITY	59,4200	7,71091	100
CONSUMER ATTITUDE	60,3000	7,51093	100

Source: Research Result, 2016 (Processed Data)

Table 4 indicates that the data used in this study as many as 100 samples of data taken from the distribution of questionnaires.

Multiple Linear Regression Model

Multiple linear regression analysis was used to analyze the hypothesis on the influence of product quality variables and consumer attitudes toward purchase decision variables. Based on the result of multiple linear regression equations, it obtained the result such as Table 5:

Table 5
Results of Multiple Linear Regression Test

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	,013	1,245		,011	,991
1 PRODUCT QUALITY	-,009	,031	-,016	-,303	,762
1 CONSUMER ATTITUDE	,579	,032	,959	18,359	,000

a. Dependent Variable: PURCHASE DECISION

Source: Research Result, 2017 (Processed Data)

Based on Table 5, the multiple linear regression equations in this study is as follows:

$$Y = 0.013 - 0.009X_1 + 0.579X_2$$

1. Value of regression constant of 0.013 means if consumer attitude and product quality = 0 then purchase decision of animal feed will increase by 1.3%
2. Regression coefficient X_1 for product quality variable was the negative value of 0,009, which means that influence of product quality variable was not exceeding in parallel with the purchase decision. It indicates that product quality variables have a negative influence in determining to purchase decision.
3. Regression coefficient X_2 for consumer attitude variable was the positive value of 0.579, which means that influence of consumer attitude is in parallel with the increasing purchase decision. It indicates that consumer attitude variables have a positive and significant influence in improving purchase decisions.

Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

The coefficient of determination is a quantity indicating that large variation of the dependent variable (purchase decision of animal feed) can be explained by the independent variable (product quality and consumer attitudes). The value of determination coefficient was determined with the adjusted R square value as described in Table 6:

Table 6
Value of Determination Coefficient (R Square)

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,947 ^a	,897	,895	1,47259

a. Predictors: (Constant), CONSUMER ATTITUDES, QUALITY PRODUCT

b. Dependent Variable: PURCHASE DECISION

Source: Research Result, 2017 (Processed Data)

Based on Table 6, the value of adjusted R Square was 0.897, which means the variable ability of product quality and consumer attitudes can describe the variation of purchase decision that was 89.7 %, while the rest of 10.3% was explained by unexamined independent variables such as price, promotion or others.

F-Test (Simultaneous)

Simultaneous/F-test was conducted to discover positive and a significance level of product quality variable and consumer attitudes toward purchase variable as described in Table 7:

Table 7
Results of Hypothesis Test in Simultaneous/F-Test ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1825,212	2	912,606	420,840	,000 ^b
	Residual	210,348	97	2,169		
	Total	2035,560	99			

a. Dependent Variable: PURCHASE DECISION

b. Predictors: (Constant), CONSUMER ATTITUDE, PRODUCT QUALITY

Source: Research Result, 2017 (Processed Data)

In Table 7, the result was F_{count} of 420,840, while F_{table} at $\alpha = 0,05$ with a degree of the numerator of 2 and F_{tabel} of 2,70. From this result, known as $F_{count} > F_{table}$ and significance of 0.000 or less than $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus, the position of the significance test point resided in the rejection area of H_0 or it can be concluded that H_1 was accepted, which means that variable of product quality and consumer attitude altogether have a positive and significant influence on purchase decision variable.

T-test (Partial)

The results of the partial hypothesis test were described in Table 8:

Table 8
Result of Partial Hypothesis Test/t-test
Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	,013	1,245		,011	,991
PRODUCT QUALITY	-,009	,031	-,016	-,303	,762
CONSUMER ATTITUDE	,579	,032	,959	18,359	,000

a. Dependent Variable: PURCHASE DECISION

Source: Research Result, 2017 (Processed Data)

In Table 8 partial test results, it obtained results as follows:

1. T_{count} value for product quality variable was equal to -0,303 less than the value of t_{table} (1.66023) or sig t value for product quality variable (0,762) greater than alpha (0,05). Based on the obtained results, thus it rejected H_0 and accepted H_1 for the working area variable. Thus, partially, the product quality has no influence and insignificant to the purchase decision. It implies that product quality has no markedly influence in determining consumer decision in animal feed.
2. Value of ac_{count} for the variable of 18.359 was greater than the value of t_{table} (1.66023) or value of sig t for consumer attitude variable (0,000) less than alpha (0.05). Based on the obtained results, thus it rejected H_0 and accepted H_1 for consumer attitude variables. Thus, partially ,consumer attitudes have a positive and significant influence on purchase decisions. It means that consumer attitudes had an influence on for purchase decision of animal feed.

DISCUSSION

Influence of Product Quality and Consumer Attitude on Purchase Decision

The result of the research carried out along with product quality, and consumer attitude had a positive and significant influence on purchase decision in heavy equipment industry in Medan city. It indicates that product quality and consumer attitudes have a significant influence on improving purchase decisions.

Influence of product quality on purchase decisions

The result of the research indicates that product quality variable has a negative and insignificant influence towards purchase decision on the purchase of animal feed in Toba Samosir regency. It was confirmed by the results of t-test analysis, which indicated that there were a negative influence and insignificant product quality towards a purchase decision.

Influence of consumer attitudes on purchase decisions

The results of the research obtained that variable of consumers attitudes has a positive and significant influence on purchase decisions on the purchase of animal feed in Toba Samosir regency. It was confirmed by the results of t-test analysis, which indicated that there were a positive influence and significant consumers attitudes towards a purchase decision.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of research and discussion described in the previous chapter, the conclusions can be drawn as follows:

1. Product quality and consumer attitudes simultaneously have a positive and significant influence towards purchase decision of animal feed in Toba Samosir regency. It was a most dominant variable of consumer attitudes in increasing purchase decision of animal feed in Toba Samosir Regency.
2. Partially, each variable of product quality has no influence and insignificant towards purchase decision of the purchase of animal feed in Toba Samosir Regency
3. Consumer attitudes have positive and significant influence on purchase decision of animal feed in Toba Samosir Regency
4. The coefficient of determination (R^2) from a variable of product quality and consumer attitudes was able to explain significant purchase decision towards purchase decision of animal feed in Toba Samosir regency equal to 89,7 %, while the rest value of 10,3% was explained by unexamined independent variables such as price, promotion or others.

REFERENCES

- i. Engel, et all. (2000). *Perilaku Konsumen*. Edisi Keenam. Jilid I. Binarupa Aksara, Jakarta
- ii. Chih-Jen Lin, Chih-Wei Hsu, Chih-Chung Chang. (2008). *A Practical Guide To Support Vector*
- iii. Kotler, Philip & Keller, Kevin L. (2009). *Manajemen Pemasaran*.(edisi 13, jilid 1). Jakarta:Erlangga
- iv. Mullins, Orville, Larreche dan Boyd. 2005. *Marketing Management : A Strategic, Decision Making Approach*, 6th edition. Penerbit McGraw-Hill. New York City
- v. Peter, J.Paul & Olson, Jerry C.(2013). *Perilaku Konsumen dan Strategi Pemasaran*. (Edisi 9, buku 1). Jakarta:McGraw-Hill Education & Salemba Empat
- vi. Salim, Abbas. (2013). *Manajemen Transportasi*. Jakarta:RajaGrafindo Persada
- vii. Schiffman dan Kanuk. (2004). *Perilaku Konsumen*.Edisi 7. Prentice Hall. Jakarta
- viii. Suryani, Tatik. (2008). *Perilaku Konsumen: Implikasi pada Strategi Pemasaran*. Edisi 1. Yogyakarta: Graha Ilmu
- ix. Sunyoto, Danang.(2009).*Analisis Regresi dan Uji Hipotesis*. Jakarta:MedPress
- x. Sunyoto, Danang. (2012). *Analisis Validitas & Asumsi Klasik*.Yogyakarta:Gava Media
- xi. Sugiyono. (2006). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif Kualitatif dan R & D*. Alfabet, Bandung.
- xii. Tjiptono. (2003). *Periklanan Yang Efektif*. PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama, Jakarta